

Deterministic control of the probabilistic spin of particles using a helical external magnetic field in quantum entanglement

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Abstract

A novel theory for controlling with 100% confidence the spin of individual particles using a specific helical magnetic external field and therefore circumventing the non-communication theorem and making possible the instantaneous transfer of information in an entangled particle pair.

1. Introduction

In QM and QE effects an entangled particle pair is called also a singlet with some properties of the two particles like spin, non-locally correlated. However, there is no transfer of information possible (i.e. non-communication theorem) therefore SR is not violated by this quantum effect. This is instantaneous-action-at-a-distance without involving information transfer (i.e. signaling) established theory says and could be also kind of non-measurable with today's apparatus superluminal action IMO.

So, why exactly we cannot use for example spin entangled pairs to transfer say bit logic information instantaneously? My search revealed for especially for the case of spin, when Bob changes the polarization of the external homogeneous magnetic field B engulfing his entangled particle say for making B field spin up, then the individual spin of the particle can end up being parallel to B thus spin up but also with equal possibility end up being antiparallel spin down during the measurement. The same goes for Alice on the far other end. If she polarizes say her external magnetic field B to be say spin up in order to make the measurement and finds that her entangled particle is spin down then with 100% confidence she can say that Bob's particle at the same time is measured to be spin up. And here is actually where the whole story ends.

Not being able to actually control the individual spin of the entangled particles and therefore not having a common reference, makes transfer of information from both sides impossible and therefore both Alice and Bob end up receiving random noise.

If the above description is correct then is it logical to prohibit that possibly there is indeed some signaling (i.e. transfer of information) involved between the two particles but the non-

communication theorem describes only our inability to resolve this signal due to the fact that we cannot actually control the spin probability of the entangled particles?

Therefore, as a conclusion the probabilistic nature of QM should not be attributed to the particles but to the observer's measurement? And therefore the measurement problem.

But what if there is actually a way to control by 100% the probabilistic spin of individual particles? According to our research this can be done using instead of a homogeneous straight flux external magnetic field B , a specific helical magnetic flux field B_H either spin up or spin down. Next we will describe why this is so, and the specific screw alike manifold this external helical magnetic field need to have.

2. The helical charge flux manifold of the electron

According to our previous research [1] of the specific charge flux manifold of an electron this is shown in Fig. 1 to be helical¹:

Figure 1 the helical on a spheroid horn torus charge flux manifold of the electron [1].

Specifically, a tangent line to the flux lines at the equator of the above shown manifold is at exactly 54.7356° angle from the vertical z-axis also know in mathematics and nuclear physics as the magic angle.

¹ Animation: <https://www.horntorus.com/particle-model/mm-index.html>

Instead of using an homogeneous straight flux lines external B magnetic field during the spin measurement, a helical screw alike magnetic flux B_H external field is used with its flux manifold similar to a left-handed screw and its step thread matching the magic angle approximate 54.73° from the vertical z -axis then we theorize that we can deterministic control the spin of the electron in an entanglement experiment either to be consistently parallel or antiparallel to the external field by switching the direction of the B_H external field from spin up to spin down or vice versa. Therefore, having now a common reference, transfer of information within the entailment pairs is made possible. Thus, opening the gate for effectively instantaneous or at least superluminal communication.

The problem with the used so far homogeneous straight magnetic flux B is that because its unitary flux manifold the electron could choose randomly if it aligns parallel or antiparallel to the B field. But using this matching angle external helical B_H the individual electron spin is forced. This is demonstrated in Fig. 2:

Figure 2 Electron can randomly orient its spin parallel or antiparallel to an external straight flux magnetic field B .

However, an helical external magnetic field B_H applied with its helix step angle matching this intrinsic charge flux manifold thread angle of the electron of 54.73° as shown in Fig. 2 will control deterministic the spin of the particle similar to a normal screw only going in or out form the hole when the threads match. There are many ways to create artificially a specific external helical flux magnetic field B_H . In one of our previous publication of a Synthetic Magnetic Unipole device [2] we have shown how this is possible, see Fig.3:

Figure 3 Screw like formation of the magnetic vortex at the centre as shown with a magnetic field viewing film created by synthetic magnetic unipole device [2].

3. Conclusion

We have shown a novel way to control determinants the probabilistic spin of the electron in an entangled pair experiment by taking into account the intrinsic charge flux manifold of the electron [1] and therefore open the possibility for transfer of information in an entanglement singlet experiment.

References

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